

AN OVERVIEW OF INFORMATION SYSTEM SUCCESS

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the extent to which the electronic information system is successful. The services provided by Information Systems are prompt and accurate, but it still has some difficulties and drawbacks, the most significant of which is a lack of protection and security systems.

Keywords: electronic information system, MIS, administrative practices

INTRODUCTION

Information has evolved into a fundamental resource for economic systems and institutions in particular. Information, whether at the macro level, such as population information systems, health information systems, industrial information systems, educational information systems, and so on, or at the micro level, must be communicated effectively and rationally [3]. Institutions should keep up with this evolution and try to rely on modern information systems to activate administrative practices and decision-making processes that improve performance [6].

An information system is a collection of interconnected components that collect, process, store, and distribute information for decision support and control in an organization [7]. They assist senior management in analyzing complex problems and issues by providing the right information at the right time, in addition to supporting decision-making, coordination, and control [9].

A. Types of Information Systems

Information systems are integrated systems that serve all administrative areas in the organization and are distinguished by the following characteristics [8]:

1. Providing complete information for planning, control, organization, and decision-making processes;
2. Serving the various departments of the organization such as marketing, production, and others;
3. Relating to the institution's past, present, and future;

B. Security Requirements For Computerized Information Systems

The goal of any information system security program is to protect the organization or facility concerned by lowering the risks that may affect the availability of information, its confidentiality, and integrity to an acceptable and specific level [4].

As a result, the institution must establish safety rules and implement security policies in accordance with generally accepted standards to ensure the system's proper operation [1]. The following elements must be studied and analyzed to ensure the security of the information system:

- a) Access control: It allows software or hardware components to be controlled in terms of preventing or allowing access to network resources [5, 11]. It can take the form of smart cards, fingerprint devices, or network communication devices.
- b) Proof of permissions: This is the process of validating a user's access to network resources. The user is identified using his name, password, or smart cards, and then permissions are granted based on his identity [8].
- c) Auditing: It is the process of verifying and tracking powers by monitoring resources and the network, and it is regarded as one of the most important aspects of network security because it identifies hackers as well as the methods and tools used to access the network [10].

Reasons for System Failure

Expected to fail at some point in time. Information Systems inability to complete their activities in the manner expected, and not finishing its operations in the time specified [2]. And there is a collection of information from factors that cause the system to fail that is represented in the following:

- a) focus on hardware rather than objectives;
- b) lack of availability;
- c) disagreement between specialist and users about artistic appropriateness;
- d) Lack of planning for the design of the information system;
- e) Inaccurate identification of the information system's capabilities;
- f) Acting reactively rather than proactively or participating;
- g) Failure to create the surrounding conditions that support the system's success;
- h) Miscalculation of the organization's future information needs;
- i) Failure to form an integrated mix of people, devices, equipment, and procedures.

The following are the most important security policies used to protect the system:

- 1- The presence of an antivirus on the servers;
- 2- Creating a unique password for each system user;
- 3- Cooling devices are housed in the server room;
- 4- Preventing the insertion of information holders (Flash Memory) into computers for any reason.

The electronic information system contributes to improving administrative practices through accuracy and speed in performance, but it has not yet reached the required effectiveness [9]. The electronic information system contributes to providing services to citizens with the required speed and accuracy, despite many errors at the level of civil status documents due to poor digitization (especially the electronic archiving); It significantly improves work performance, but because it does not cover all areas and applications for all municipal interests, it is not considered an integrated system.

The computerized information system requires work to reduce the severity of the resistance to change caused by the traditional culture of the departments, because employee resistance would cause the electronic information system to fail to achieve the desired goals.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we attempted to highlight the importance of the electronic information system and its role in the electronic management, Information Systems has helped to improve administrative practices, particularly the services provided to citizens. As a result, the most important findings can be summarized as follows:

1. The electronic information system contributes to improving administrative practices through accuracy and speed in performance, but it has not yet reached the required effectiveness;
2. The electronic information system contributes to providing services to citizens with the required speed and accuracy, despite many errors due to poor digitization (especially the electronic archiving);
3. It significantly improves work performance, but because it does not cover all areas and applications for all interests, it is not considered an integrated system.

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